

Pilot Evaluation 8: Fostering business-academia cooperation

Final Version

Francisco Javier Pérez Trujillo

Summary

The purpose of this pilot is to develop a preliminary prototype of a common catalogue of research groups and transferable research activities at the Una.Resin level, and ultimately, examine the potential for creating a catalogue in the future. This pilot project, thus, addressed the following transformation modules: enlarge the scope of R&I activities by fostering business-academia cooperation, and promoting cooperation between research groups.

Universities cannot exist in isolation from society. Close collaboration between academia and business brings benefits to both researchers and industry. Two main needs were identified and, then, addressed in the preliminary prototype to promote business-academia cooperation:

- The need to promote cooperation between different research groups, which is essential to be able to respond to complex industry demands. The pilot project started by fostering such cooperation, providing researchers with access to information about the activities and characteristics of other research groups within the Alliance.
- The need to identify and give visibility to the activities developed by the research groups that can be transferable to industry. The pilot, thus, sought to collect this information and make it accessible to potential users.

The **outcome** of this pilot project is a prototype of research groups and a transfer catalogue (Una.Transfer | Una Europa (una-europa.eu)). If this information (research groups/transfer activities) is shared at the Alliance level, in an accessible and simple way, the different universities could benefit in several ways. For example, increased international collaborations between research groups will be established. Moreover, the markets for transferable research activities at international level will be widened. The pilot has produced a highly accessible prototype that synthesises the main results. A final version of this prototype could be shared with the general public in the future.

Based on the **lessons learnt** from this pilot project, it is important that the Alliance and participating universities provide a framework that both allows information to be easily shared and quickly identifies transferable activities that can promote business-academia cooperation.

Objectives and aims of the pilot project

The purpose of this pilot is to develop a preliminary prototype of a common catalogue of research groups and transferable research activities at the Una.Resin level. Through this preliminary prototype, the possibilities of creating a catalogue in the future will be examined. Hence, this pilot project addressed the following transformation modules: enlarge the scope of R&I activities by fostering business-academia cooperation, and promoting cooperation between research groups.

The pilot project sought to initiate desired institutional change by fostering business-academia cooperation with the aim of enlarging the scope of R&I activities, and promoting networking between researchers. To support the achievement of this change, the intended audiences of the pilot project are researchers, businesses and industry engaged in R&D, citizens, and

NGOs, with the beneficiaries being the universities of the Una.Resin Project.

Initial design and implementation of the pilot project

The analysis carried out in a previous mapping exercise within Una.Resin (see Una.Resin Deliverable 3.1) shows that the main challenge for the universities, regarding business-academia cooperation, is the overall coordination of activities undertaken by different units/agendas to ensure synergy effects.

Two main needs were identified to promote business-academia cooperation:

- The need to promote cooperation and information sharing between research groups and foster contact between researchers from other countries, disciplines, etc. This sharing will ensure an up-to-date understanding across groups and of individual knowledge and skills and, ultimately, support academia in offering the highest quality services to industry.
- The need to improve the way in which information about research groups is shared with industry and to identify and give visibility to the activities performed by the research groups that can be transferable to industry. Many research groups can offer different services to private companies, the third sector, governmental organisations, etc. However, the services they can provide are sometimes unknown to potential users. A necessary first step in bringing academia and business closer is to give visibility to the "transferable research activities". Complementary to this, sharing information between universities through a catalogue could also be very advantageous.

These two emerging needs lead to the main goal of the project of developing a research groups and transfer catalogue. First, desk research was carried out and clusters/WPs were consulted to identify recommendations. After that, a prototype was developed. Following a meeting with the PSC where the initial pilot was presented, comments and feedback from the Una.Resin members were taken into account and the pilot was updated. In addition, a meeting with WP1 (within which recommendations for a collaboration platform were being developed) was held to develop synergies that can benefit Una.Resin as a whole. These meetings highlighted the need to focus the pilot on the Focus Areas of Cultural Heritage and One Health, and simplify the consultation process among the Una.Resin members.

A proposal on how to share information about research groups and transferable research activities and a proposal for a fact sheet on how to collect the information were shared with the WP3 and the PSC. After integrating the received feedback, the following principle good practices were identified to overcome possible challenges:

- Focus on specific areas of knowledge to make the pilot more accessible. This reinforces the previously stated idea of focusing on the areas of One Health and Cultural Heritage.
- Clearly define the information to be shared in detail with universities.
- Make the information collection process as simple as possible. Ideally, an automated way of collecting information should be developed. At this early stage, it is not necessary to collect a large amount of information since the target is the production of an example catalogue. A short questionnaire was adequate that could then be improved and expanded in the future.

The biggest challenge was gathering the necessary information. To overcome it, an online

questionnaire was created.

Outcomes and impact of the pilot project

A prototype of a research groups and transfer catalogue has been built. If this information is shared at the Alliance level, in an accessible and simple way, the different universities could benefit in several ways. Firstly, they could see the international collaborations between research groups increasing and, secondly, there could be a widening of the markets for transferable research activities at the international level. More precisely, universities will improve the way in which information is shared about their research groups and their transferable activities, which is currently challenging. Moreover, they will be able to gain this information at an international level, which will support the important work carried out by the relevant offices of each university.

The pilot has produced a prototype that is easy to use and which synthesises the main results so they are widely accessible. A final version of this prototype could be shared with the general public in the future, and act as an example of good practice in information exchange.

Sustainability of the pilot project

This pilot could be scaled up in Una.Futura project if there is agreement between the Alliance members. The scaled-up version could cover all Una Europa Focus Areas and offer a public online platform with information on research groups and activities transferable to industry. The benefits are superior to the costs, with the resulting costs split between two main categories: IT personnel (one person can be in charge of the platform) and researchers' time (for filling out the online survey to provide details about their activities). Scaling up the pilot could lead to a framework for promoting collaboration among Alliance members, as well as business-academia cooperation.

Lessons learnt

A series of lessons have been identified from designing and implementing the pilot:

- Researchers are supportive of a framework that fosters business-academia cooperation.
- The benefits are superior to the costs, especially as the framework needs to allow for information to be easily shared.
- It is important to ensure ample visibility of the research teams' activities that are transferable to industry activities so as to enhance the business-academia cooperation.

Recommendations for the future

The pilot offers a number of recommendations giving direction to future activity:

- This pilot should be scaled up in Una.Futura.
- The scaled-up version should address all Una Europa Focus Areas.
- The prototype developed within this pilot project could be transformed into a publicly accessible online platform with information on research groups and activities transferable to industry.